

An Empirical Evaluation of DeepAR for Univariate Time Series Forecasting^{*}

Ricardo Urjais Gomes^{1,2}[0000-0002-1814-071X], Carlos Soares^{1,2,3}[0000-0003-4549-8917], and Luis Paulo Reis^{1,2}[0000-0002-4709-1718]

¹ Faculty of Engineering, University of Porto

up202003374@up.pt, {csoares, lpreis}@fe.up.pt

² Artificial Intelligence & Computer Science Lab.(LIACC – member of LASI LA), University of Porto

³ Fraunhofer AICOS Portugal

Abstract. DeepAR is a popular probabilistic time series forecasting algorithm. According to the authors, DeepAR is particularly suitable to build global models using hundreds of related time series. For this reason, it is a common expectation that DeepAR obtains poor results in univariate forecasting [10]. However, there are no empirical studies that clearly support this. Here, we compare the performance of DeepAR with standard forecasting models to assess its performance regarding 1 step-ahead forecasts. We use 100 time series from the M4 competition to compare univariate DeepAR with univariate LSTM and SARIMAX models, both for point and quantile forecasts. Results show that DeepAR obtains good results, which contradicts common perception.

Keywords: Time Series Forecast · Probabilistic Forecast · Deep Time Series

1 Introduction

Time series forecasting is a challenging task, with increasing importance and widespread application. It has been applied in areas such as retail demand forecast [4], energy management [15], electricity consumption [1] and tourism flows [2].

Traditionally, time series forecasting has been dominated by linear methods like Auto-Regressive (AR), Moving Average (MA), and a combination of both,

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the ARIMA models, or Holt-Winters, since they are well-understood and effective on many problems [7]. However, most of these models face several issues, such as: being restricted to linear relationships, fixed temporal dependency, and focus on short-steps forecast [1, 15]. More complex algorithms, such as LSTM, although able to map more intricate patterns, still fall short, for instance, when there are long-memory processes to be forecasted.

A method that has become popular is DeepAR, an AutoRegressive deep learning LSTM-based model [12]. It has a specific encoder-decoder architecture, different from common *seq2seq* architectures, in the sense that DeepAR uses the same architecture for both the encoder and decoder, with weight sharing. A unique feature of DeepAR is the use of the output of the LSTM layer to parameterize a distribution function assumed for the data. This is used to make probabilistic forecasts. Simply put, the model fits the bias and weights of its encoder-decoder model and the parameters of a distribution function.

Distribution assumptions enable DeepAR to build prediction intervals for the target at test time [12]. One author, however, signals that these distribution assumptions may be too tight to deal with real-world data [5]. Furthermore, one of the most significant advantages of DeepAR may also be one of its flaws: DeepAR performance stands out when enormous collections of data are available [10]. This means that, as its authors acknowledge, DeepAR is not a good option for univariate forecasting.¹ Although some studies report mixed results on the performance of DeepAR in the univariate setting [9, 11, 8, 3], their results are domain-specific (e.g. wind power generation) and tested on a small set of time series. Comparison between DeepAR and ARIMA on monthly competition datasets (M3) is limited and inconclusive. Results indicate that DeepAR is slightly better than ARIMA but the difference doesn't seem significant [14].

The goal of this work is to investigate the hypothesis that DeepAR is not suitable for univariate time series. For this purpose, we do not compare it with state-of-the-art models for univariate time series, which are naturally expected to obtain the best possible results. Instead, we compare it with standard models, namely a univariate LSTM model and a SARIMAX model, which enable us to assess whether DeepAR is suitable for univariate time series forecasting. The three models are tested on 100 diverse time series from the M4 competition [10]. Comparisons are made both for point forecasts and also for predictive intervals. Our results show that for univariate scenarios, DeepAR provides better results for point and percentiles forecasts than LSTM and SARIMAX, both for MAPE, MASE and wQL metrics. This challenges the common perception that DeepAR is competitive only when trained on hundreds of time series.

The paper is organized as follows: the next section details SARIMAX, LSTM, and DeepAR models (Section 2). In Section 3, the experimental setup and data description are given. Section 4 includes the main findings and their analysis. In the last section, conclusions are presented.

¹ <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/sagemaker/latest/dg/deepar.html>

2 Time Series Forecasting

In the following section, we start by formalizing the notion of time series. Next, briefly summarize SARIMAX and LSTM, which are the reference models, and, finally, we present DeepAR.

Time Series Let $z_t = \{z_{t=1}, z_{t=2}, z_{t=3}, \dots, z_{t=J}\}$ be a set of values that comprises a time series, where J is the length of the time series. Forecasting implies choosing a prediction horizon h up to which one wants to forecast. The forecasted time series will then be $\hat{z}_{t_0+h} = \{z_{t_0+1}, z_{t_0+2}, z_{t_0+3}, \dots, z_J\}$. Here, t_0 is assumed to be the point up to which the model is trained. Time series forecasting can be divided into univariate regression or multivariate regression. Univariate regression implies that future values of z_t are only predicted by its own past values. Multivariate implies that other time series or categorical variables are used to estimate future \hat{z} values.

For both univariate and multivariate time series, linear and non-linear models are used for time series forecast. The most established linear model is arguably ARIMA models (and its variants). As for non-linear models, neural network architectures (especially LSTM algorithms) are one of the best-established ones.

SARIMAX [7] extends the ARIMA model, $\Phi_p(B)(1-B)^d z_t = \Theta_q(B)\epsilon_t$ with hyperparameters p , d , and q , with seasonal hyperparameters $(P, D, Q)m$ that represent the seasonal behavior and n external regressors to capture linear or changing trends in the data. An important step is setting the values of the hyperparameters, which can be defined manually, although some software packages automate the process using grid search [7]. The strong assumptions that make SARIMAX a very clear method reduce its flexibility. This means that, since many real-world applications do not verify the assumptions, the forecasting ability of the method is reduced.

LSTM is a type of Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) [6]. It uses a hidden state in each cell to ensure that previously generated information is stored and transmitted to the next cell. Additionally, it uses a cell state to implement a long-term memory [6]. The algorithm then combines the signals from both states to generate the output of the network. LSTMs have been very successful on natural language processing (NLP) tasks but have some limitations for time series forecasting, namely because of the longer size of the sequences and the type of dependencies between sequential data.

DeepAR is a recent algorithm [12] that has become very popular in forecasting. It was designed for global time series forecasting although it can also be used for univariate time series. DeepAR creates a global model, i.e., it models a conditional distribution of the future of all the time series:

$$P(z_{i,t_0:T} | z_{i,1:t_0-1}, x_{i,1:T}) \quad (1)$$

where t_0 is the time point from which each target time series $z_{i,t}$ is unknown, and $x_{i,1:T}$ are covariates that are assumed to be known for all future time points. The conditional distribution is based on LSTM but also on distributional assumptions for the time series. This enables probabilistic forecasts.

During the training process, DeepAR natively samples several training examples randomly from the training set and the algorithm estimates the parameters of the distribution for all horizons (left of Figure 1) using the LSTM output and the true value of $z_{i,t}$. In this phase, the model behaves as an autoregressive LSTM that outputs distribution parameters at each time step for the time series. The choice of the distribution is upon the user. At test time, DeepAR behaves as an encoder-decoder model. In order to get many steps-ahead predictions, each sampled value for a given time $t_0 + h$ is fed back as input to build the next prediction (right of Figure 1). The probabilistic forecasts are given by several estimates based on Monte Carlo sampling. The estimates are sampled from the trained distribution. With several estimates for the forecast, quantile forecasts are also generated.

Fig. 1. Train (left side) and test (right side) of DeepAR algorithm, reproduced from [12]

More formally, if data is assumed to follow a normal distribution, then $z_{i,t}$ is parametrized by $\theta_{i,t} = (\mu, \sigma)$. The loss function is then the Gaussian likelihood function, $\ell_G(z_i|\mu, \sigma) = (2\pi\sigma^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \exp[-\frac{(z_i-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}]$. Both parameters μ and σ are estimated with two dense layers that use the output $h(t)$ of the LSTM layer (Equations 2 and 5, respectively).

$$\mu(h_{i,t}) = w_\mu^t h_{i,t} + b_\mu \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma(h_{i,t}) = \log(1 + \exp(w_\sigma^t h_{i,t} + b_\sigma)) \quad (3)$$

During the training phase (left side of Figure 1), at each time step t , the inputs to the model are the covariates $x_{i,t}$, the target value at the previous time step $z_{i,t-1}$, and the previous network output hidden state $h_{i,t-1}$. The LSTM then outputs its hidden state $h_{i,t}$. This output is used to compute the parameters $\theta_{i,t} = (\mu, \sigma)$. Since μ and σ are a function of the LSTM output, then $\theta_{i,t}$ is also a function of $h_{i,t}$ and Θ , where Θ represents the parameters of the LSTM layer in

DeepAR. The task during training is to maximize the Gaussian Log-Likelihood function: $\mathcal{L} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{t=t_0}^T \log p(z_{i,t}|\theta(h_{i,t}))$. Details for other distributions are given in [12]. We note this is different from SARIMAX and LSTM: In SARIMAX there is no assumption on the data distribution upon fitting the model, but the normality of residuals must be verified. As for LSTM, there are no assumptions on the probability distribution of data, neither on the residuals.

When forecasting (right side of Figure 1), the past values of the time series until z_{i,t_0} are fed into the model. The forecasts for $t_0 + h$ are then conditioned by the previously predicted values for the time series. The model samples a prediction value, given the previous hidden state and sampled value. To obtain the probabilistic forecasts, the prediction for each time step is repeated, by default, 100 times [12].

3 Experimental Setup

The section describes several important issues concerning the design of the experiments: the data; the preparation of training and testing instances, the configuration of DeepAR, LSTM and SARIMAX; how probabilistic forecasts were obtained; and how train and test sets are built and how predictions are evaluated.

Data The data for this study was obtained from the M4 competition, which encompasses a wide range of domains, including Industry, Finance, Demographics and others [13]. We randomly selected 100 monthly datasets.

No data pre-processing was carried out, including algorithm-specific operations, as discussed below. Additionally, all the used data does not contain missing values. The selected data have diverse characteristics in terms of length, seasonality, and potential cumulative effects. This is important for the generality of the results.

Instance Preparation The representation of each instance is affected by the hyperparameters *context length* and *prediction length* (Figure 2). Context length controls how many prior values of the series z up to any time t are used as input features. Prediction length controls how many steps-ahead the model should forecast. The context length size (d) and prediction length (h) are used as follows: for a point t in the time series, the window of observations z_{t-d}, \dots, z_t is used as input features, and the goal is to predict the value z_{t+h} . This is the standard setting for DeepAR, while for SARIMAX and LSTM it had to be specifically implemented.

The context length d was set to 30 for all the algorithms. This choice tries to capture long latent seasonalities in the monthly data. Having at least 12 periods of data is necessary to capture monthly seasonal patterns, and selecting 30 periods allows for capturing longer seasonalities. All the models are trained for a prediction length of one step-ahead ($h = 1$).

Fig. 2. Train (left side): the horizontal lines represent the conditioning (d) and prediction (h) lengths. Test (right side): conditioning starts with d observations prior to t_0 (i.e. t_0 , representing the point after which testing is done), while the prediction length is applied to unseen data. Evaluation is done for this set of data (adapted from [12])

Algorithm Configurations The algorithms considered have very different sets of hyperparameters, and their sensitivity to their values is also different. This means that designing a fair experimental setup is a challenge. However, given that the goal of the project is to assess if DeepAR is competitive with two standard algorithms and also as it has shown robust behavior with default values [9], we decided not to carry out any hyperparameter tuning. If we were to tune its hyperparameters, this could create an unfair advantage over the other two algorithms. Naturally, as DeepAR is based on LSTM, we also did not do any hyperparameter tuning for the latter. Finally, considering our goal once more, we need SARIMAX to achieve minimally competitive results. Since a default ARIMA(1,0,0) model would just resemble a random-walk model [7], we, therefore, selected the values of its hyperparameters using grid search, as described below.

SARIMAX The estimation of (p,d,q) and (P,D,Q) orders was done with all the instances in the training set for each series. In order to get the best possible model, a grid search was built to find the (p,d,q) and (P,D,Q) parameters that maximize the fit to the time series. This grid-search was done to search several models with different (p,d,q) , (P,D,Q) orders, m seasonal cycles, and differencing d factors. The search space is defined in Table 1. The selected values were those that delivered the lowest Corrected Akaike’s Information Criterion (AICc). No seasonal differencing was applied, and neither log transforms.

Table 1. Value range for grid-search in SARIMAX fitting

	p	q	P	Q	m
max_value	5	5	2	2	[4, 6, 12]
min_value	2	2	1	1	

LSTM LSTM models are built with a simple architecture: two hidden layers with 50 units each and a dense layer of 1 cell for output. The metric loss is an

equally weighted MAPE and MSE loss. The model is trained for 50 epochs with a default batch size of 32. No scaling or normalization was done on any data.

DeepAR DeepAR was also configured with a simple architecture: the number of hidden layers is 2, and the number of cells per layer is equal to 40. Default hyperparameters are also used: the assumed distribution output is set to Gaussian; the model was trained for 50 epochs; the batch number was set to 50; and the number of generated Monte Carlo samples to generate prediction intervals was equally set to 100. In the context of this work, no covariates $x_{i,t}$ were used.

Probabilistic Forecasting Unlike DeepAR, LSTM does not produce probabilistic forecasting and SARIMAX is highly dependent on the normality of the residuals. To derive prediction intervals for the LSTM and SARIMAX models, we adopt the fitted residuals bootstrapping method [7]. For linear models where the distribution of fitted residuals follows a Normal distribution, the 90% prediction interval is calculated as $\hat{z}_{t_0+h|z_{1:t_0}} = \pm 1.64\hat{\sigma}_h$. It is important to note that this formulation tends to be overly simplistic, often resulting in narrower prediction intervals [7]. Bootstrap from residuals only assumes that errors are uncorrelated. The error of a model for a prediction $\hat{z}_{t|t-1}$ is given by $\epsilon_t = z_t - \hat{z}_{t|t-1}$. This way, one can extract all the fitted residuals of a model. The 1 step-ahead prediction of z_t is given by $z_{t_0+1|z_{1:t_0}} = \hat{z}_{t_0+1|z_{1:t_0}} + \epsilon_{t_0+1}$. Since the true value of ϵ_{t_0+1} is unknown, we assume future errors to be similar to past errors and replace ϵ_{t_0+1} by a randomly sampled fitted error ϵ_t , with replacement. This is repeated multiple times to estimate the empirical distribution of z_{t_0+1} . Then, one can obtain the prediction interval by estimating the percentiles from this empirical distribution. This procedure can be applied to linear models (SARIMAX) and non-linear models (LSTM). The number of generated sample paths was 100.

Evaluation The models are trained with data from $t = 1$ to t_0 where t_0 marks the 80% data used for training. t_0 is marked by the green vertical line in Figure 2. During the training of the SARIMAX and LSTM models, instances are processed sequentially in time, while, for DeepAR training, the next training instance is selected randomly. This behavior is standard to DeepAR. Testing is done on the 20% data following t_0 , using a sliding window.

Taking t_0 as the reference point starting the evaluation, the first prediction ($h = 1$) is given by:

$$\hat{z}_{t_0+h|z_{1:t_0}} = \hat{f}(z_{t_0-d+h}, \dots, z_{t_0}) \quad (4)$$

where \hat{f} is the 1 step-ahead trained model.

For point predictions (i.e. mean values), only MAPE and MASE metrics were used (Equations 5 and 6). Since the goal is to average the error performance among the 100 time series, point prediction errors should be scale-free.

$$MAPE(z, \hat{z}) = \text{mean} \left(\sum_{t=t_0}^J \frac{|z_t - \hat{z}_t|}{|z_t|} \times 100 \right) \quad (5)$$

$$MASE(z, \hat{z}) = \text{mean} \left(\frac{\sum_{t=t_0}^J |z_t - \hat{z}_t|}{\frac{1}{t_0-1} \sum_{t=2}^{t_0} |z_t - z_{t-1}|} \right) \quad (6)$$

Where T is the training set, t_0 is the point from where predictions start, and J refers to the length of the time series. For quantile predictions, Mean Pinball Loss (MPL) was used for the 5th, 50th and 95th. Since Pinball Loss (PL , defined in Equation 7) is not a scale-free metric, all MPL errors were divided by the sum of the test set of each series, referred to as Weighted MPL (wQL)(Equation 8). This ensures that one can take average errors across all the 100 time series avoiding the bias effect of larger scale errors in some particular series.

$$PL(z_\tau, \hat{z}_{\tau}) = \begin{cases} (z_t - \hat{z}_t)\tau & \text{if } z \geq \hat{z} \\ (\hat{z}_t - z_t)(1 - \tau) & \text{if } \hat{z} \geq z \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

$$wQL(z_\tau, \hat{z}_\tau) = \frac{\sum_{t=t_0}^J PL(z_\tau, \hat{z}_\tau)}{\sum_{t=t_0}^J z_t} \quad (8)$$

where τ is the target quantile. The forecast error for each method on the test set was averaged across all time series so broader comparisons could be done.

4 Results and Discussion

In this study, the primary objective was to evaluate the predictive performance of the DeepAR model on univariate time series data, compared with standard models that are commonly used for this task. Our results challenge the widely accepted claim of DeepAR’s poor results in univariate setting. This perception is yet very present in the forecasting community [10]. Both the mean and the median of the error metrics for point and probabilistic forecasts obtained by DeepAR are lower than those of LSTM and SARIMAX (Figures 3 and 5). We start with the presentation of the results in detail for point forecasts and probabilistic forecasts. Then, we discuss the robustness of the algorithms. Finally, we summarize some limitations of the study.

Point Forecasts Concerning MAPE, DeepAR obtains a mean value of 0.083, while for LSTM it is 0.39, and for SARIMAX is 0.5. This indicates that, on average, the forecasted values by the DeepAR model deviate from the actual values by approximately 8.3%, while LSTM and SARIMAX deviate from the actual values by approximately 39% and 50%. The median MAPE values confirm this observation: DeepAR obtains 0.072, while for LSTM the value is 0.30 and for SARIMAX it is 0.24.

The results with MASE also support the previous conclusions. The mean MASE of DeepAR is 7.2, while LSTM and SARIMAX obtain 13.67 and 19.21, respectively. Additionally, the median MASE of DeepAR is 2.34, while LSTM and SARIMAX, obtain median values of 4.97 and 3.80, respectively.

Fig. 3. MAPE error and MASE error on the test set

We also analyzed the relative difference of performance of DeepAR compared to LSTM and SARIMAX models, trying to identify patterns in the time series for which it is either much better or obtains very similar performance. Some of the cases where the advantage is clear are presented at the top of Figure 4. We observe that, in these series, the trend changes and there is no clear seasonal pattern. The bottom of the same figure illustrates the case where the difference in performance between DeepAR and the other two models is not clear. These are time series that are either short and noisy (M82 and M19) or where the seasonal pattern is clear (M15). This seems to confirm the idea that DeepAR needs a significant amount of data to achieve good performance, as pointed out by the authors. On the other hand, as SARIMAX is properly designed to handle seasonal data, it achieves similar performance to DeepAR.

Fig. 4. Best performing (top-row) and worst performing (bottom-row) time series for DeepAR, in terms of MAPE metric, in relation to LSTM and SARIMAX models

Overall Quality of Models Our results indicate not only that DeepAR is better than LSTM and SARIMAX but, according to the MAPE values, they are generally good. However, the results obtained with MASE indicate that all the algorithms obtain a higher error than the naive forecast (i.e. $\hat{z}_{t+1} = z_t$). This may be due to a limitation of MASE, which compares the *test error* of the model with the *training error* of the naive forecast. Although it is the standard formulation of MASE, it assumes that the distribution of the values of the time series in the training and test sets is the same, which is not guaranteed. Further analysis is required to investigate this.

Probabilistic Forecasts DeepAR also performs better than LSTM and SARIMAX according to the wQL measure (Figure 5). For all quantiles, the low errors observed indicate that the prediction interval generated by DeepAR is sufficiently wide to cover the out-of-sample values of the data. As with point predictions, the median performance of the DeepAR model for all quantile error metrics is slightly smaller than the mean. This means that, although the majority of the results are good, there are a few time series for which the forecasting performance is quite bad.

Fig. 5. wQL error for the 5th percentile (left side), 50th percentile (center) and 95th percentile (right)

As for wQL, DeepAR also stands out. This means that DeepAR fits the distribution parameters effectively, not only for univariate point forecasts but also for prediction intervals. Results for SARIMAX and LSTM are worse than those obtained for DeepAR. The lower errors of DeepAR for all quantiles imply that its prediction intervals are built around good estimates of the true value of z , as indicated by the point forecast results. Furthermore, neither SARIMAX and LSTM were not originally designed for probabilistic forecasting and we adapted them for that purpose using a simple method. For more precise results, an individual analysis on each series results, in their true scale, would be advisable to draw more concise conclusions.

Robustness The similarity between the mean and median MAPE values obtained by DeepAR indicates a consistent performance across datasets. On the other

hand, the comparison between the mean and median MASE results, indicates that DeepAR struggles to predict some of the series. The difference between the observations based on MAPE and MASE provides further evidence that this may be due to time series where there is a change in concept, leading to a higher error in the test set than in the training set.

Both for MAPE and MASE, the mean for the two reference algorithms, SARIMAX and LSTM, is much higher than their median. This clearly shows that both algorithms have not fitted/generalized quite well in some of the series. This lack of fitting/generalization is very severe in some of the models, skewing the mean of all the metrics to the low-performance side. Additionally, it can be observed that, although the mean performance of SARIMAX is always worse than LSTM, the median value is better.

Limitations The process of model generation was not optimized. All the models were trained with default settings. No scaling, normalization, or smoothing, was done. LSTMs, for instance, are sensitive to initialization, number of units, or scaling, which can largely affect the mean models' performance. On the other hand, data transformations may also help SARIMAX upon fitting to data, providing perhaps better mean forecasts. For DeepAR, adding more units to the LSTM layer, defining different initializations, or adding layers to the model could also improve its forecasts. This is an important limitation, although it is out of the scope of this work. On the other hand, all algorithms were treated equally, leading to unbiased results.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

We have empirically studied the predictive performance of univariate DeepAR model against two state-of-the-art models. The results were obtained for 100 time series and compared in terms of point prediction metrics and prediction intervals metrics.

Our results show that DeepAR consistently outperforms standard methods in univariate forecasts for short-term, both for point and interval forecasting. These results expand on the argument that DeepAR is competitive in a univariate forecasting setting, as they contribute to contradicting common knowledge regarding the bad behavior of DeepAR in this setting. The results present in this study are encouraging since may trigger a new round of studies that systematize for which conditions DeepAR is competitive with state-of-the-art models that generally take the lead in these forecasting settings.

Further investigation on the same experimental setting should include improved LSTM architectures, linear models based on trend and seasonality description, and more advanced models such as Prophet or N-BEATS. Hyperparameter tuning will also be a way to check how well each model performs for this data set. Furthermore, more datasets should also be used to systematize better our findings, along with multi-step forecasting scenarios.

References

1. Afrasiabi, M., Aghaei, J., Afrasiabi, S., Mohammadi, M.: Probability density function forecasting of electricity price: Deep gabor convolutional mixture network. *Electric Power Systems Research* **213**, 108325 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.epr.2022.108325>
2. Dong, Y., Xiao, L., Wang, J., Wang, J.: A time series attention mechanism based model for tourism demand forecasting. *Information Sciences* **628**, 269–290 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2023.01.095>
3. Eikeland, O.F., Hovem, F.D., Olsen, T.E., Chiesa, M., Bianchi, F.M.: Probabilistic forecasts of wind power generation in regions with complex topography using deep learning methods: An arctic case. *Energy Conversion and Management: X* **15**, 100239 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecmx.2022.100239>
4. Fildes, R., Ma, S., Kolassa, S.: Retail forecasting: Research and practice. *International Journal of Forecasting* **38**(4), 1283–1318 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2019.06.004>, special Issue: M5 competition
5. Ge, D., Pan, Y., Shen, Z.J., Yuan, R., Zhang, C.: Retail supply chain management: a review of theories and practices. *Journal of Data, Information and Management* **1**, 45–64 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42488-019-00004-z>
6. Hewamalage, H., Bergmeir, C., Bandara, K.: Recurrent neural networks for time series forecasting: Current status and future directions. *International Journal of Forecasting* **37**(1), 388–427 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2020.06.008>
7. Hyndman, R., Athanasopoulos, G.: *Forecasting: Principles and Practice*. OTexts, Australia, 2nd edn. (2018)
8. Jungbluth, A., Lederer, J.: The deepcar method: Forecasting time-series data that have change points (2023), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.11241>
9. Karanikola, A., Liapis, C.M., Kotsiantis, S.: A Comparison of Contemporary Methods on Univariate Time Series Forecasting, pp. 143–168. Springer International Publishing, Cham (2022). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-76794-5_8
10. Makridakis, S., Hyndman, R.J., Petropoulos, F.: Forecasting in social settings: The state of the art. *International Journal of Forecasting* **36**(1), 15–28 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2019.05.011>
11. Papastefanopoulos, V., Linardatos, P., Kotsiantis, S.: Covid-19: A comparison of time series methods to forecast percentage of active cases per population. *Applied Sciences* **10**(11) (2020). <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10113880>
12. Salinas, D., Flunkert, V., Gasthaus, J., Januschowski, T.: Deepar: Probabilistic forecasting with autoregressive recurrent networks. *International Journal of Forecasting* **36**(3), 1181–1191 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2019.07.001>
13. Spiliotis, E., Kouloumos, A., Assimakopoulos, V., Makridakis, S.: Are forecasting competitions data representative of the reality? *International Journal of Forecasting* **36**(1), 37–53 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijforecast.2018.12.007>
14. Spyros Makridakis, Evangelos Spiliotis, V.A.A.A.S.G.M., Nikolopoulos, K.: Statistical, machine learning and deep learning forecasting methods: Comparisons and ways forward. *Journal of the Operational Research Society* **74**(3), 840–859 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1080/01605682.2022.2118629>
15. Zhang, Z., Qin, H., Liu, Y., Yao, L., Yu, X., Lu, J., Jiang, Z., Feng, Z.: Wind speed forecasting based on quantile regression minimal gated memory network and kernel density estimation. *Energy Conversion and Management* **196**, 1395–1409 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2019.06.024>